

An Uncomplicated Method of Diagnostic Approach to Type 2 Klippel Feil Syndrome and Review

Sandhya Jalagam¹, Anusha Nareddy², Adimulam Josthsna³, Seggam Deepthi⁴

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatrics, CAIMS, Karimnagar

²Post Graduate, Department of Radiology, CAIMS, Karimnagar

³Post Graduate, Department of Radiology, CAIMS, Karimnagar

⁴Post Graduate, Department of Radiology, CAIMS, Karimnagar

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Anusha Nareddy

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Abstract

Klippel Feil Syndrome is a very rare disease with three different types of presentations. Most of the cases commonly show the clinical triad of short neck, low posterior hair line, and limited neck movements. But less than 50% of all patients show all these three clinical features. We are reporting a very rare case of 12-year-old male patient presenting with neck and body pains for duration of two months. Whole spine CT revealed complete assimilation of anterior & posterior arches of C1 vertebra with clivus and occipital bones, defect at left posterior arch of C1, Aplastic right posterior elements and hypoplastic dens of C2 vertebra. Plain CT chest revealed hypoplastic right 1st and 3rd ribs with widened intercostal spaces at the levels of these hypoplastic ribs. There are only two great vessels arising from the arch of aorta which are left subclavian artery and a common trunk which is giving off, right brachiocephalic trunk and left common carotid artery and where again the brachiocephalic trunk is dividing normally into the right subclavian and right common carotid arteries. Plain CT and MRI abdomen revealed empty left renal fossa and with a 5.7x2.2 cm sized kidney with hilum facing anteriorly noted in right lumbar region [which is small sized, ectopic in location and malrotated left kidney]

Keywords: Atlanto-occipital assimilation, Partial aplasia of C1, Hypoplastic dens, Hypoplastic ribs, Ectopic and malrotated kidney.

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Introduction

Klippel Feil syndrome was initially reported by Maurice Klippel and Andre Feil from France in 1912[1]. Klippel Feil syndrome is characterised by segmentation failure of one or more cervical vertebra, with or without thoracic and lumbar vertebral segmentation anomalies [2]. Type 2 is the most common form of Klippel Feil syndrome. The inheritance pattern of these congenital abnormality is usually sporadic. But sometimes it may be autosomal dominant or autosomal recessive. Estimated to occur one in 40,000 to one in 42,000 newborns worldwide [3]. We are reporting a very rare case of type 2 Klippel Feil syndrome with short neck, cervical spine & ribs abnormalities, Aortic arch with branching vessels anomalies and renal anomaly [ectopic and malrotated kidney].

Case Report

A 12- year-old male with neck and body pains since 2 months. Patient had no restriction of neck movements, no signs of any motor or sensory disturbances, no cranial nerve problems, no vascular compromise, or involuntary movements.

Antenatal, intranatal and postnatal periods were uneventful. Baby was a product of non-consanguineous marriage. Term baby with birth weight of around 2.25 kg, cried immediately after birth. All milestones attained according to age. Immunized as per national immunization schedule.

Whole spine CT reveals complete assimilation of anterior and posterior arches of C1 vertebra with clivus & occipital bones [4] and defect at left posterior arch of C1, Aplastic right posterior elements and hypoplastic dens of C2 vertebra. On plain CT Chest scan, hypoplastic right 1st and 3rd ribs with widened intercostal spaces at the above levels are noted. There are only two great vessels arising from the arch of aorta which are left subclavian artery and a common trunk which is giving of right brachiocephalic trunk and left common carotid artery and where again the brachiocephalic trunk is dividing normally into the right subclavian and right common carotid arteries. Plain CT abdomen scan revealed empty left renal fossa and with a 5.7x2.2 cm sized kidney with hilum facing anteriorly noted in right lumbar region [which is the small sized ectopic and malrotated left kidney]. Further contrast

study was not done as the patient was not cooperative. Mild 'S' shaped scoliotic curvature of lower cervical and upper dorsal spine is noted. Then dedicated MRI Brain was done for further evaluation.

MRI Brain imaging revealed normal brain parenchyma with vertebral anomalies. As patient is asymptomatic conservative treatment was given and advised for follow up scans.

Figure 1: Blue and Red arrows showing complete assimilation of C1 vertebra with clivus and occipital bones.

Figure 2: VRT Reconstruction CT - BLUE arrow showing Atlanto-occipital assimilation, black arrow representing defect at left posterior arch of C1 Vertebra and orange arrow representing partial aplasia of right posterior element of C2 Vertebra.

Figure 3 and 4: CT axial images - RED arrow represents partial aplasia of left posterior arch of C1 and BLUE arrow represents partial aplasia of right posterior elements of C2.

Figure 8: VRT Reconstructed CT image – Blue and red arrows showing hypoplastic 1st and 3rd right ribs.

Figure 9 and 10: MR Coronal and axial images - Black arrow showing right kidney in right renal fossa. Red arrow showing empty left renal fossa. Blue arrow showing small sized ectopic, malrotated left kidney in right lumbar region with hilum facing anteriorly.

Discussion

Type 2 Klippel Feil syndrome is the most common variety of all the types. It consists of congenital segmentation anomalies at the cervical spine regardless of number of vertebral bones involvement. In cervical spine, most commonly involved segment is C2-C3, followed by C5-C6 vertebral levels and then cranio-vertebral junction. Klippel Feil syndrome is sometimes detected on imaging as an incidental finding as most of the patients present with complaints that are unrelated to the syndrome. Sometimes patients present with visceral, neural, spinal abnormalities with cosmetic issues. These patients may show accelerated degenerative changes at the level of vertebral fusion which may cause spinal cord compression.

Klippel Feil syndrome was originally classified by Maurice Klippel and Andre Feil into 3 subtypes.

TYPE 1: Is Characterised by fusion of many cervical and upper thoracic vertebrae [4].

TYPE 2: Is characterised by fusion of 2 or 3 vertebrae with associated hemivertebrae, atlanto-occipital fusion [5] or other cervical spine anomalies. It is the most common of all subtypes. It shows either autosomal dominant or autosomal recessive inheritance pattern [6].

TYPE 3: Cervical spine fusion with lower thoracic or lumbar vertebral involvement.

Association anomalies with Klippel Feil syndrome are Sprengel's deformity of the shoulder, anomalies of the aortic arch and branching vessels, spinal scoliosis, cervical spondylosis, and renal abnormalities [unilateral renal agenesis, renal ectopia].

Plain radiograph and CT coronal and sagittal imaging are necessary for the diagnosis. MRI is indicated in patients with neurological deficits. MRI is gold standard in demonstrating degenerative changes in spine, canal stenosis and cord compression [7].

We are reporting a case of type 2 Klippel Feil syndrome with occipito-atlantal fusion, partial aplasia of C1 vertebra, aplastic right posterior elements with hypoplastic dens of C2, hypoplastic ribs, aortic arch and branching vessels anomalies and renal anomalies.

Conclusion

Klippel Feil Syndrome is a very rare disease with three different types of presentations. We are reporting a type 2 Klippel Feil syndrome case associated with ribs, renal, aortic arch, and its branching vessels anomalies. CT is the gold standard investigation in diagnosing spinal and vascular abnormalities as the complete abnormalities will not be visible on MRI scan.

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